

Knowledge management opportunities at Meili

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Summary

I carried out the knowledge management opportunities survey and information clinics at [MeiliSearch](#) in December 2021 and January 2022 when we had a total of 22 staff.

This report examines the quantitative and qualitative data I obtained from these interactions, makes recommendations for what we should stop, keep, and start doing across different areas of our work, and concludes with next steps to kick off the action phase.

Context

MeiliSearch is a tech startup founded in 2019, based in France, with colleagues in four different countries, and a mixture of office-based and remote working.

Participation in the research project was optional. I made the knowledge management opportunities survey available to all colleagues at Meili on Tuesday 7th December 2021, and responses were accepted until the end of Monday 20th December 2021. At this time, 22 people were employed at Meili. For those who opted in to the information clinic stage, these interviews took place in late December 2021 and early January 2022.

Research methods

I needed to find out about the current situation at Meili, and identify opportunities for improving our knowledge management practices. Participation was optional, and I received a total of 16 responses from 14 people (from a possible 20, discounting me and a colleague who is currently on parental leave). This response rate of 70% is a good return.

My investigations involved three methods:

1. Survey part A - quantitative questions
2. Survey part B - qualitative questions
3. Information clinic - qualitative discussion

Contents of the survey

Part A: Q1-10 invited responses on a scale of 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree (quantitative)

1. It's difficult for my team to make decisions
2. It's hard to find relevant information at the time of need
3. We have to start from scratch each time we start a new project
4. We repeat the same mistakes
5. It's difficult to find out if anyone else has already done similar work
6. Information is poorly communicated to me
7. I can't find standard processes/templates/techniques
8. I don't know how to find experts to help me
9. We are unable to respond effectively to users
10. It takes too long to design and deliver services to our users

Part B: Q11-13 were free-response questions (qualitative)

11. Tell me about your information pain points

12. Tell me about any examples of good information sharing, recording, or reusing that you know are already happening

13. Is there anything else you would like to add, suggest, or ask?

The final question gave the **opportunity to book an information clinic**

14. Finally, would you like to book a 25-minute "information clinic" session with Laura to talk further about your ideas and suggestions, or explore together some possible solutions to a problem you've identified?

All questions were optional.

Respondents were asked to reply once from the perspective of each team of which they're a member.

Q1-10 are phrased in the negative to encourage participants to consider and examine their information pain points, as this gives me the most useful leads for areas where we can make improvements.

Format of the information clinics

I met with each participant individually, and scheduled a call for 25 minutes. In most cases, our session lasted longer, and in future I will allow 50 minutes.

I explained to each participant that I would give them 3-4 prompt sentences one at a time using the video call chat function, and invited them to respond to each. To avoid interrupting the participant, my role was to make notes and speak only to seek clarification. Many participants responded enthusiastically and gave me a lot of useful information.

Examples of prompt sentences

- I feel frustrated at work when...
- My work flows really well when...
- When I imagine good teamwork at Meili, I think of...
- Someone who communicates well is [name] because they...
- My opinion about our meetings is...
- Communicating asynchronously means...
- Working across many time zones will...
- We should be better at documenting...
- I have this expertise which is little known or used at Meili...
- My understanding of Meili's product vision is...
- We know the scope of our roles by...
- We record our decisions by...

Confidentiality

Respondents were invited to give their name and team, and these details were used to help with interpreting the results (and in some cases going back to the respondent to seek clarification).

Although I know who said what, respondent names and teams are not included in the results in order to provide some degree of confidentiality, and encourage us all to focus on *what was said* rather than who said it.

Quantitative results from the survey

- Respondents were asked to respond once for the perspective of each team they're a member of, but one respondent combined their answers, hence the entry Team = [Multiple]. This is why there are more responses than participants.
- Blank cells indicate that no response was given.
- These numbers are intended to be used as informal indicators, as the sample size and population involved are too small for formal statistical analysis.
- Cell shading: darker shading indicates stronger agreement, and therefore areas of opportunity for improvement

Team	1. It's difficult for my team to make decisions	2. It's hard to find relevant information at the time of need	3. We have to start from scratch each time we start a new project	4. We repeat the same mistakes	5. It's difficult to find out if anyone else has already done similar work	6. Information is poorly communicated to me	7. I can't find standard processes/ templates/ techniques	8. I don't know how to find experts to help me	9. We are unable to respond effectively to users	10. It takes too long to design and deliver services to our users
[Multiple]	1	3		1	3	1	3	5	1	5
Cloud (SaaS)	2	2	1	3	1	2	4	5	5	2
Cloud (SaaS)	3	1	1	3	1	2	4	4	3	2
Core	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2
Core	2	3	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	4
Core	1	1	1	2	2	1		4	2	2
DevRel	1	2	4	3	1	1	4	2	2	3
Documentation	3	2	4	2	3	2	4	1	2	2
Documentation	4	4	2	1	4	4	3	2	2	2
Human Resources	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	1	3	3
Human Resources	2	2	5	2	1	3	3	2		
Integrations	1	2	3	1	2	2	2	1	1	2
Integrations	3	3	2	2	4	2	1	3	2	3
Integrations	1	1	1	2	4	2	1	4	1	4
Product Management	3	3	2	4	3	2	3	4	2	4
Senior leadership team	4	2	4	3	1	3	2	4	3	4
Sum	34.00	34.00	35.00	36.00	36.00	31.00	40.00	46.00	32.00	44.00

Quantitative results: general findings

- The more responsibility a person has in the Meili staff structure, the more likely they are to notice information gaps.
 - ◆ This suggests that managers are doing a good job of providing clear information to their teams, and we need to continue our work to improve communications, coordination, and decision-making at the managers' level.

- The less a person's role directly involves our code base, the more likely they are to notice information gaps.
 - ◆ This suggests that although we have clear priorities and processes for our developers, we need to continue our work to improve strategic planning and team scope for those working in other teams, such as DevRel, Product, Documentation, and Cloud (SaaS).

What's going **well** - these areas received positive responses overall

6. Information is poorly communicated to me
9. We are unable to respond effectively to users

What's **not going so well** - these are the most obvious trouble spots

7. I can't find standard processes/templates/techniques
8. I don't know how to find experts to help me
10. It takes too long to design and deliver services to our users

And we can also seek to make improvements in these areas which received **mixed responses**

1. It's difficult for my team to make decisions
2. It's hard to find relevant information at the time of need
3. We have to start from scratch each time we start a new project
4. We repeat the same mistakes
5. It's difficult to find out if anyone else has already done similar work

Qualitative results from the survey and information clinics

I've arranged participants' feedback by topic, to make it easier to identify the main themes which emerged from our exchanges. Many of the topics are connected, rather than being absolute categories. Of the 14 individual respondents to the survey, 6 opted in for an information clinic.

What do you appreciate (or not) about our meetings?

Weekly team meetings are valued for the chance to *“organize and share”* the team's work. Some people find short (15 min) daily meetings useful for talking about *“the problems that we might encounter”* but for others *“they are a waste of time, a hole in my day”*.

In concert with other improvements to support asynchronous working, we need to reduce our reliance on meetings that don't have a clear purpose and outcomes, and **improve our meeting rituals**. This is partly practical: as our staff expands and we are scattered across more time zones, it's impossible for our meeting load to grow with it. It's also a leadership issue: improving our exploration of problems and possible solutions, division of roles, and prioritization should be happening at the weekly meeting, supporting continuous asynchronous communication. Being able to call each other for a quick discussion to clarify those points will continue as a just-in-case option, but not a routine event.

Recommendations for meetings

- Stop: having meetings that don't have a clear purpose
- Keep: checking in with each other
- Start: preparing for and structuring our meetings.

What do you appreciate (or not) about our processes?

Responses varied according to the point of view of the participant. For example, examples of good processes included our Github practices - *“Our processes are public in <https://github.com/meilisearch/integration-guides/tree/main/resources>. Also, we have central issue in the same repo here: <https://github.com/meilisearch/integration-guides/issues>”*.

However, as one participant observed, *“the processes of each team might work ok within each team, but obscure for outsiders, our practices and rituals, how do we organize ourselves”*. An example of how this could cause problems was *“when I need to work with Team A, who do I address, how, what info to provide, what will the result be, how long will it take?”*. Integrating such requests into a single project management workflow (such as [Jira](#)) was suggested, and following a common template to ensure all relevant information is provided at the start. This would increase efficiency and reduce mental load.

Related to this, some participants commented that as our staff expands and we start working across more time zones, we will need to have clearer policies on aspects of work life such as *working hours* (the hours you work in a given week at times you choose), your *available hours* (times you must be online for meetings and exchanging with colleagues through other mechanisms). It was acknowledged that since the beginning there had been little formality about this as for the first few years, Meili colleagues were also friends, and were in the same time zone (if not all at the Paris office).

Recommendations for processes

- 🚫 Stop: siloing our processes within each team - much of our work involves or affects other teams
- 👉 Keep: good processes in Github
- 🌱 Start: following a common process for projects, detail the aims and scope, and give more information at the start to help the project advance faster once under way.

How do you find the information you need to do your job?

Our colleagues at Meili make use of many information resources in their everyday work. Respondents are very positive about our technical documentation:

- *"The documentation of MeiliSearch is always up to date and helps a lot in all my MeiliSearch related questions"*
- *"The integration guide repository is very very useful for me to quickly find almost all of the information I need."*
- *"I find it easy to access the information that I need 99% of the time. For technical needs, we have a relatively clean codebase that explains itself 70% of the time, and for the remaining 30%, we have good internal communication within the team."*

For colleagues in non-dev roles, the picture is different:

- *"There is not really anyone that I can rely on internally. So my main information source is the Internet (and book)s. That is a large amount of information, and I have to filter it on my own."*
- *"I often need to ask for info, it's not just available by default. [Several colleagues have made periodic efforts to] summarize what will be done and how, or what a particular team is doing [but it's not systematic]."*

Our internal documentation needs to be restructured: *"I have a feeling that in my team we communicate a lot, but this information transmission is not necessarily well structured, and sometimes it is hard to find it again at the moment it is needed."*

The number of different tools we use means that information is scattered and siloed, it's difficult to tell which is the most up-to-date, and it means having to search in multiple places to find anything:

- *"I find it difficult to know where I should search for information : Notion ? Slack ? Github ? Usually I search in those 3 until I find my answer 🤔"*
- *"I also struggle to remember where a useful information was posted in Slack... I think that there are too many channels / they can have more explicit names / we should set "rules" to know where to post information"*
- *"There's lots of info on Github (in different repos) but it's hard to find and summarize it. There's also a lot on Product Board but we don't all have access - we can see and vote, but not access the detail."*
- *"Our information pipeline could definitely use work. When we ask questions about MeiliSearch the software internally, we usually do it in four main public channels: #core-engine, #dev, #product, or #integrations. This does make it a bit hard to find those answers later, since it involves the extra step of remembering which channel it was asked in and filtering through the noise. I think we technically have the answer to every question we've asked about MeiliSearch at our fingertips, but it doesn't feel very accessible."*

This is exacerbated by the lack of consistent templates or structures for recording information that could be useful to someone else. We also need to improve our habits about moving work-in-progress Slack discussions

to a searchable knowledge base (such as Github) where the exchanges can be useful to future conversations, even if it's too early to make a decision on the subject today. This will go a long way towards reducing duplication of effort.

Recommendations for finding information

- 🚫 Stop: exchanging information only in Slack, where it's hard to find later
- 👉 Keep: using the tools we already have but not adding anything extra without making a case for it first
- 🌱 Start: write shorter summaries of your work, more often, and put them where others can find them.

How do you reuse work that's already been done at Meili?

"One of my information pain points is knowing if there is a developer who has already faced the same problem/implementation challenge."

Across the board, participants recognized that we have a wide range of skills and experience among our colleagues, both from their time working at Meili and elsewhere. However, **we are not yet good at recording and sharing this knowledge**. As a result, **teams sometimes duplicate work**, which wastes their time rather than learning from the same or similar work which has already been done by someone else - *"My pain point is when I figure out the [redacted] team does not use the tool of the [redacted] team and codes from scratch"*.

"We lack experience at Meili, so we have to infer rather than inspire/research" - this is partly because the team at Meili is young (average age 29) and therefore does not have the same wealth of workplace and sector experience as do more established organizations. It's also partly because we're innovating, and therefore we're often facing original challenges.

"I am very often working on new features or with new technologies that I don't necessarily master, but that haven't been used by the team before. So many of my actions require some research and making choices and decisions that I don't necessarily know if they are the best. In this case I need to often consult the team about those choices. It would be interesting to have access to experts or people with experience to ask specific questions about those choices."

However, as one participant put it, we're *"only inventing the search engine, not everything else around it"*, and can probably afford to **copy or adapt existing good practices for many other areas** of our work.

A good opportunity to reuse and review existing documentation is through the onboarding process. New colleagues have the fresh perspective necessary to spot what's missing and what can be improved, as well as being well placed to contribute to the documentation as part of their initial tasks. This transforms their onboarding to a much more interactive experience, as they can get involved with a practical activity, such as cleaning a repo, documenting a process, gap analysis, or preparing a presentation on a project.

Recommendations for reusing work

- 🚫 Stop: starting from scratch - check what's already been done
- 👉 Keep: finding out what works elsewhere and reusing it
- 🌱 Start: using the fresh perspective of new colleagues to tell us what's missing from our documentation (internal and external).

How do you keep on top of news and notifications at work?

As much of our current communication involves Slack messages in real-time, keeping on top of things is tricky. It's even harder when you return from time off - *"Information on what happened when I come back from holiday is not always easy to get"* and *"when I come back from holiday: I have to guess some changes (coming from the top), and I have to ask for them instead of having an already dedicated meeting/notion page to be up to date"*.

Many of our meetings involve giving updates in real time which could more efficiently be written down, and then explore any implications during the meeting - *"In our [team] meetings, [redacted] tells us what happened in the [redacted] team, so that we know what will come and impact us."*

A central change in the expansion of the company will involve relying less on exchanging information in real time (otherwise our calendars will be all meetings and no deep work). Instead, we will shift towards doing more reading and writing. This is good for several reasons:

- taking the time to read and write helps us think more carefully about what we're communicating
- the better you describe an issue, the quicker it can get done. Refinement (defining the parameters) of an issue becomes smoother as we get better at defining it well from the beginning.
- it automatically leaves a record as it's already documented
- our meetings should become more interesting as we focus on exchanging opinions in our time together, rather than describing a situation
- it helps with triage, as the small barrier to writing an outline issue means you think twice about how important it is (you can always use a 'bucket of random ideas' document to note quick thoughts by theme and then see which become important enough to explore properly)
- it makes it easier to get back to work after a period of absence, especially when we refine our information workflows to synthesize the main themes from the detail of the everyday.
- it naturally supports asynchronous working, allowing people to work flexibly
- it helps onboard new staff, and colleagues changing role

However, it will require a change of mindset from all of us:

- we will set aside time every day to read updates and respond where necessary
- we will arrive at meetings having read the background information for each agenda item in advance, and make notes on how we can contribute to the discussion
- we will facilitate meetings more proactively and prepare ahead to avoid a 'cold start'.

Recommendations for news and notifications

- 🚫 Stop: relying on Slack to catch up after time away from work
- 👉 Keep: using team meeting notes, but write summaries rather than transcripts
- 🌱 Start: spending time every day reading and responding in asynchronous documents.

How do you keep up with what else is happening at Meili?

- *"I find it difficult to get a broad view of the company's activities. The new Heartbeat format should probably help, but to be honest I haven't read the last one yet. There's a lot of text in that document and it's hard to know which bullet points are important which makes it take longer than it should. Feels like it could (and should) be condensed a bit more."*
- *"we have to find time to read everyone's updates on top of the meeting"*

- *“Nobody reads the written sections... [names] don’t look for info, they just listen, don’t read.”*

We are currently implementing changes to the fortnightly all-staff Heartbeat meeting, which now features fewer presentations but in more depth. Updates from all teams were previously done as a series of short presentations but are now done as written notes. As we progress with the new style, we will help improve everyone’s skill in abstracting the key information that will be useful for other teams to know about, rather than providing a list of actions completed. So these updates will become more useful as we get better. We need to reinforce to staff why these changes are being made, and the expectation that all of us need to take time to contribute and read the updates, as this is not yet understood by everyone.

“I tried in the past to communicate very often on the current [team] process, I slowed down a bit on this part, I will make efforts on this.”

It’s a lot of effort to produce updates without an existing rhythm to help you structure and coordinate your communications with other teams. By **mapping our information workflows** and establishing a communications pattern, we will make it easier to pass on the right information to the right people at the right time. The Heartbeat meetings are a key part of this.

Recommendations for keeping up (information workflows)

- 🚫 Stop: sending messages to groups of people without a specific purpose. No more updates which resemble a list of tasks achieved recently
- 👉 Keep: contributing team updates to the Heartbeat notes...
- 🌱 Start: ... and do it smarter: give context, explain why it’s important, ask for specific input or feedback.

How do we work together towards common goals?

Another pain point is the **absence of a shared roadmap** of each team’s projects and how they work together to support Meili’s organizational goals - *“I would like to have a clear vision of every project’s deadlines. Too much information is [just] shared in the office and not shared to the rest of the company.”*

This is not just a problem for leaders attempting to coordinate efforts across the organization. The concentration of this information in informal exchanges in the Paris office also **excludes the majority of colleagues who work remotely**.

“I think it would be great to have more vision about the work and the future perspectives of other Meili teams and MeiliSearch itself.” Having a common understanding of how individual, team, and organizational projects complement each other is important in **building a shared culture at work**. *“We should have a better understanding of the whole Meili concept, what we plan to do and evolve. We get different visions from each of the cofounders - I’d prefer to have one unified vision and build on it. There is conflict between the cofounders’ vision and priorities, and no view beyond 3 months from anyone.”*

It’s also essential in making sure that we are all **working towards the same objectives**, or at least in harmony with them - *“I feel frustrated at work when... we do not agree on what we want to achieve with MeiliSearch, the product vision, values of MeiliSearch as a product. Feel like we’re losing the accessibility and simplicity aspects. Our promise was to be very simple, that message is being lost. Who is the guardian of that? Can cause tensions with colleagues when we don’t have a shared understanding.”*

Recommendations for common goals and shared strategy

- 🚫 Stop: developing team plans in isolation from the rest of the company
- 👉 Keep: being interested in what all our colleagues are doing
- 🌱 Start: creating all-Meili roadmap and priorities so we can see opportunities for collaboration between our projects, and plan to avoid any conflicts or delays.

How do we define the scope of our roles?

In a small organization, our roles are necessarily broad. However, we can improve our information workflows to be **clearer about each person's expertise and autonomy**, and **streamline who is involved in which decisions**.

Some non-dev participants report frustration that their expertise is sometimes debated rather than accepted as a programmer's might be:

- *"Today my biggest pain point is that I have too often conversations about naming. For me it's surface, where the real feedback should be done on the actual functioning of the feature and its UX."*
- *"I feel frustrated at work when... when I have to do lots of back-and-forth on the same theme, such as trying to explain something technical. Root issue is perhaps a combination of (1) lack of technical knowledge among colleagues, (2) my difficulty in explaining it to them, and (3) lack of clarity about roles and responsibilities, so rather than my decision being recognized, we end up debating it."*
- *"I also have a role as [redacted] referent that is not always taken completely seriously despite my past experience."*

Another brake on our capacity to innovate quickly is spending a **disproportionate amount of time on minor decisions** that could be modified later on - "I feel like I'm repeating myself and going in circles, I'm thinking in particular of the [issue] when the impact we're trying to have is going to be centralized for a small part of our users."

This lack of boundaries seems to affect non-dev roles the most. *"I think some people sometimes don't really know what the outlines of my role are (either because I haven't done a good job at communicating them, or because they simply aren't used to working with [redacted] and are used to doing everything themselves). This can result in decisions taken or information conveyed that I won't be aware of, although they affect my job."* And *"we should clarify that the Docs team are experts for language, not coding. If it's too hard to document, it's not a good solution."*

*"How do we know the scope of our roles (what my job includes and what it doesn't)... that's a really good question! Not sure it's written down anywhere... If you're just arrived, the only way you'll know is by asking them. And it's hard to ask them, feels too direct. **It's hard to know who does what.**"* and *"My scope evolves organically. Sometimes I take on a role because if I don't do it, no-one else will."*

To avoid such traps, we should clearly delineate who is the **expert for each domain**, and **trust their professional judgment**. Good documenting of the decisions we make will allow for future changes, and should be a good way to demonstrate that our experts made wise decisions. *"We don't decide because we feel it's not our legitimate role to make that call."* Trusting our domain experts will build their confidence and allow us to innovate more quickly by not debating every point with everyone.

Poorly-defined roles are adding to the mental load for everyone, as they don't know where to focus their efforts: *"I'm not sure what I'm supposed to do and what I'm best at... Where do people expect me to be active? What I need is KPIs, objectives for me. Tell me what you expect from me, give me specific responsibilities and give me feedback about how I'm doing. I could be better at each thing but I'm doing too much at once."*

Loosely defined roles also contribute to **information overload and lack of focus**. *"I also struggle knowing what could impact me / what is important / which subject I should dig into. Sometimes, I see big PR's [pull requests] on github passing, and I would love to take the time to read them all, but I don't have it. I would love to know which are important for me and I should definitely read, and which I could simply forget."* For some of us who are accustomed to being widely involved in Meili projects, a clearer delineation of roles will require us to give up some control, but in doing so we devolve responsibility to other colleagues, helping to build trust between us all.

As Meili grows, it's no longer possible to consult everyone on everything as it might have been in earlier times when the staff numbered only eight or fewer. We can mitigate the sprawl of scope creep by:

- better record-keeping about who made a decision, when, and based on what (even if the answer is "nothing much"). This also helps with future review, as many problems need iterative decisions rather than being decided once forever.
- exploring a problem fully before jumping in with a solution. If you struggle to write 250 words to outline a Github issue, it's likely that the problem is not yet well understood, and you need to explore it better before asking others to commit time to it. Proposing possible solutions gives a practical starting point for deciding next steps.
- distinguish between issues which need wider consultation and those in which an expert can directly implement their preferred solution.
- apply an information cascade model such as DACI (Driver, Approver, Contributor, Informed) or RACI (Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, and Informed) to clarify roles and responsibilities for a given issue. The more our roles specialize, the more often we will be informed rather than consulted about decisions being made in other teams.

Recommendations for defining the scope of our roles and responsibilities

- 🚫 Stop: rushing to implement a solution before properly exploring and defining the problem
- 👉 Keep: being willing to try out different roles and areas of expertise
- 🌱 Start: defining clear responsibilities for different aspects of a project, and link this to accountability for the outcomes.

What will shifting towards asynchronous working mean for us?

"Communicating asynchronously means... better expression when writing in a text, better than short messages when everyone's involved at once [Slack], doing better work, go further in thinking. It can take longer [at first] but c'est un mal pour un bien [it's a blessing in disguise] as it means we can do more in parallel".

Asynchronous working is not yet happening at Meili. At the time of writing, this is because although we have a staff of 22 in four countries (and even most of those in France aren't based at the Paris office), we don't yet have to work across many time zones. 21 of us are in the same time zone, and one person 3 hours ahead.

We need to concentrate on developing full equity of access to information at work between those working remotely and those based at the Paris office. As our staff grows and we are joined by colleagues in a broader

range of time zones, we will have to start thinking about asynchronous practices which until now have not been urgent.

“Communicating asynchronously is essential in reducing our reliance on meetings for everything. Async working would force us to have more autonomy, and it would make it quicker to make a case - I wouldn't have to wait for a meeting to share something.”

Asynchronous working involves a lot of reading and writing - it's not just about being able to have a more flexible work day and respond when you choose. We need to adopt the practice of taking time to read and write to make async a success.

Recommendations for shifting towards asynchronous working

- 🚫 Stop: relying on meetings to move forward with a project
- 👉 Keep: documenting our work as we go
- 🌱 Start: use collaborative editing and comments to exchange ideas and make decisions.

What do we currently document or communicate well?...

Participants gave numerous examples of good communication or documentation that's already happening:

- *“A few months ago, Kero did a video presentation about how the core engine is working technically speaking. I found it awesome and would like to see more initiatives like this one.”*
- *“The specs of the search engine”*
- *“I also really love the Heartbeat meetings, as it is a moment when we can share important things and be aware of what's happening inside MeiliSearch”*
- *“We reuse some parts of the specifications in the docs”*
- *“DevRel did a great job recently explaining what they do, what's on their roadmap, how to communicate with community members, etc.”*
- *“I love how Clementine has been using the #ms-releases channel on Slack. It has been hugely helpful for our work.”*
- *“Thomas did a good job in the Heartbeat about future plans for SaaS.”*
- *“I also love that everybody is always present to answer some questions on Slack.”*

Colleagues appreciate **updates for non-specialists**: accessible and understandable to those who don't work in that area, but still need to know what's going on in other teams and can learn from and be inspired by their projects.

As well as sharing their updates, colleagues enjoy the **contact** that these interactions bring, and the opportunity to **recognize and celebrate success** together. As one participant said, *“people love being celebrated, even if they say they don't. A simple compliment can make a huge difference.”*

Participants appreciate others' responsiveness on Slack. We can further improve by encouraging discussions away from direct messages (not searchable and don't permit others to take part) to channels (closed if necessary); and moving work-in-progress Slack discussions to a searchable knowledge base where the exchanges can be useful to future conversations.

... And what can we document or communicate better?

Participants' ideas included:

Documentation in general

- *"Documentation, especially in open source repositories."*
- *"Notion documents."*
- *"[redacted] writes huge articles with long specifications."*
- *"We are a small team and we are building a big product... we tend to not write everything since we are always talking together. We use GitHub issues/board/milestone as a tool for us to record what needs to be done and when, this can be improved as to be better organized and described, but again the problem is that we have a lot to do right now and want to keep going. Although I think we would be less 'stressed' and maybe a bit more productive if we did a bit more describing/organization."*

Processes and best practices

- *"Most of our processes need to be better documented."*
- *"Understanding Github Core/Integrations teams' issues is not easy, how do they work? Who's responsible for what? It's not obvious to me. I manage ok because I've had experience of this already. But we need to put in place some best practices."*
- *"It's not currently part of our agile sprint to write a brief summary, but we should. Taking time at the end to do a retrospective will make the next sprint better."*
- *"We rotate around people to review and sign off, often people do this too quickly just to get it out of the way."*

Prioritize and synchronize

- *"We often prioritize and re-prioritize again next day, which adds a lot of noise to what are we doing and what we need to progress on (but we are getting better)"*
- *"I think we need to learn how to make a decision and stick to it, we tend to often rethink or retalk about things that we already chose/prioritized. This is because of 2 things I think, we have a lot on our plate in a small team (need to adapt and go from product to project to development etc.) and because we should structure more the things we think and write exactly what we chose and why. We need to understand that we can still come back after and change what we did but at least if we stick to what we chose, we have something done and working in which we can improve later."*
- *"I would also like to improve the prioritization process even if I am quite satisfied with it today. What is missing is time to be ready in advance and start communicating earlier internally and externally."*
- *"It's hard for many teams to prioritize. How can we help them to improve their everyday work? We could improve this by better synchronization of the teams. I need to understand how I can help other teams by working with them from time to time."*

Structured communications

- *"I feel like we are missing out on sharing knowledge with other teams that could help them but also us out. For example amongst the devs, we share the same technical field but we do not share any of our experiences or knowledge between teams. I would love to know about their technical challenges or technology choices. For example I would love to see how other teams architected their projects."*

- *"We sometimes struggle to know which of [redacted]'s specifications are important for us (in other words, important for the users), and which are purely important for our developers."*
- *"I think it would be great also to have a small presentation on each release showing what is added and how it impacts MeiliSearch even if the more less obvious details as to be very aware of everything instead of through the blog post or the github issues."*
- *"It is not very clear to me what the process is around demos. Who should maintain them, how should they be put forward as very few people in MeiliSearch know they exist. It happened a lot that team members were surprised when I told them we had interactive demos and they almost all told me "but where can we find these??"... this shows that other teams may not know or are not in a dynamic of finding out what others do."*
- *"Overall we communicate a lot, try to write down as much as we can about what we will do and when, but this needs to be structured a bit more I think, to help us get through the issues quickly and smoothly but also onboard new people."*
- *"I would like more visibility on what we will do as a company. Record decisions somewhere we can all access them. I discover things in the releases... we need a structure for passing on information about decisions we've made [for info, not discussion]. If I know it's there I will go and look for it."*
- *"I'm trying to involve people early on in projects so they don't come and criticize later. I'm not sure how to improve this, as I can't involve everyone at every stage. Maybe I need to split things out into several steps, and be clearer about the feedback or opinions I need from my colleagues."*
- *"I would love to know more about what we find out about our users."*

Ways we can improve:

- **atomize** the issues or topics you raise. If a subject is tangled, separate out the different strands. Then you can more easily distinguish the bits you can do something about now from those you can't, and it's easier to follow the logic of decisions that were made and their downstream consequences.
- **explain simply** - the more simply you can explain something, the better you understand it. Take the time to abstract your issue away from the detail, and focus on the main problem to solve or questions to explore. Assume that your colleagues are intelligent, but not that they have the same specific knowledge as you.
- **write** to help you think through a problem. Don't waste others' time in a meeting by working out what you mean as you're saying it.
- **read** to help you research different options
- **focus** - make lists, prioritize. Do a smaller number of tasks well.
- **use templates** to structure our writing - for making PRs, collating team updates for the Heartbeat meeting summary, meeting notes... Write less but do it better!

Recommendations for documenting and communicating

🛑 Stop: working so much in reactive mode which is stressful and inefficient

👉 Keep: periodic updates for everyone about different projects or areas of work (a rotation will be planned into the cycle of Heartbeat meetings and there's space to suggest spontaneous contributions too)

🌱 Start: mapping our information workflows - who needs to know what, when, and why (see DACI/RACI information cascade model above).

Support for improving knowledge management at Meili

Finally, it was encouraging to discover colleagues' active support for KM work - *"it's a very good initiative and I think you can help a lot to help me better communicate and organize myself on these aspects"* and *"je trouve ça très chouette comme initiative"* [I find this initiative very cool].

Combined with a clear view of the gaps and opportunities for improvement, this appreciation will be a great help in collectively realizing the recommendations for what we can do better.

Participants appreciated taking part in the information clinics: *"it's hard to get this opportunity to step back and have a wider perspective of what we're doing at Meili [and in my team]. It's valuable to help us look at ourselves."*

All the recommendations in one list

Recommendations for meetings

- 🚫 Stop: having meetings that don't have a clear purpose
- 👉 Keep: checking in with each other
- 🌱 Start: preparing for and structuring our meetings.

Recommendations for processes

- 🚫 Stop: siloing our processes within each team - much of our work involves or affects other teams
- 👉 Keep: good processes in Github
- 🌱 Start: following a common process for projects, detail the aims and scope, and give more information at the start to help the project advance faster once under way.

Recommendations for finding information

- 🚫 Stop: exchanging information only in Slack, where it's hard to find later
- 👉 Keep: using the tools we already have but not adding anything extra without making a case for it first
- 🌱 Start: write shorter summaries of your work, more often, and put them where others can find them.

Recommendations for reusing work

- 🚫 Stop: starting from scratch - check what's already been done
- 👉 Keep: finding out what works elsewhere and reusing it
- 🌱 Start: using the fresh perspective of new colleagues to tell us what's missing from our documentation (internal and external).

Recommendations for news and notifications

- 🚫 Stop: relying on Slack to catch up after time away from work
- 👉 Keep: using team meeting notes, but write summaries rather than transcripts
- 🌱 Start: spending time every day reading and responding in asynchronous documents.

Recommendations for keeping up (information workflows)

- 🚫 Stop: sending messages to groups of people without a specific purpose. No more updates which resemble a list of tasks achieved recently
- 👉 Keep: contributing team updates to the Heartbeat notes...
- 🌱 Start: ... and do it smarter: give context, explain why it's important, ask for specific input or feedback.

Recommendations for common goals and shared strategy

- 🛑 Stop: developing team plans in isolation from the rest of the company
- 👉 Keep: being interested in what all our colleagues are doing
- 🌱 Start: creating all-Meili roadmap and priorities so we can see opportunities for collaboration between our projects, and plan to avoid any conflicts or delays.

Recommendations for defining the scope of our roles and responsibilities

- 🛑 Stop: rushing to implement a solution before properly exploring and defining the problem
- 👉 Keep: being willing to try out different roles and areas of expertise
- 🌱 Start: defining clear responsibilities for different aspects of a project, and link this to accountability for the outcomes.

Recommendations for shifting towards asynchronous working

- 🛑 Stop: relying on meetings to move forward with a project
- 👉 Keep: documenting our work as we go
- 🌱 Start: use collaborative editing and comments to exchange ideas and make decisions.

Recommendations for documenting and communicating

- 🛑 Stop: working so much in reactive mode which is stressful and inefficient
- 👉 Keep: periodic updates for everyone about different projects or areas of work (a rotation will be planned into the cycle of Heartbeat meetings and there's space to suggest spontaneous contributions too)
- 🌱 Start: mapping our information workflows - who needs to know what, when, and why (see DACI/RACI information cascade model above).

Next steps

My 2022 KM roadmap projects [internal link] are grouped around the main three KM themes of **collecting** (store, search), **connecting** (transfer, share), and **creating** (apply, acquire) information. These categories are often interdependent. Improving any single aspect will have positive effects on the others; improving several aspects in parallel has a powerful multiplier effect.

You can see the recommendations from this report on the roadmap, along with my three strategic themes for KM:

1. Employee **onboarding**: getting colleagues up to speed quickly (reduces business costs and affects our ability to scale the company).
2. **Strategic alignment**: building a shared roadmap based on a common understanding of our organizational vision, mission, and strategy (and making sure everyone in the organization understands when there's been a shift in direction and adjust accordingly).
3. Meili **knowledge base** and its management: starting with making the most of the existing key content repository (Notion).

As one participant said *“we shouldn't go on as we are... making some changes would mean we'd all feel better at work. And it's funny that we can iterate on Meili but not on our ways of working”*. Bearing that in mind, these recommendations are intended in a spirit of exploration and iteration.

- The recommendations can be attempted individually but will be most effective if a team commits to making a change together.
- We don't all need to do everything at once: for example, a team might choose 3-5 aspects that are particularly important to them, and build from there.
- It's helpful to have a buddy or peer mentor outside your team so you can talk to each other about how you're getting on and seek advice.
- Across our staff we are lucky to have people with a range of expertise so if you'd like to be put in touch with someone who can help teach you a skill, please ask.
- Applying a new skill directly in your work is the best way to learn something.
- Creating a culture of coaching and peer learning allows all of us to be multipliers of the skills we're sharing.

The nature of the problems exposed at Meili is similar to that found at many organizations. By hiring a Head of Knowledge Management and working together to make improvements, we are taking action to prevent these issues becoming intractable problems as the company grows. Even in large organizations where some of these problems will already have taken root, it's never too late (or too early!) to take action to improve our knowledge management practices.